

Urdhwaga Gati of Vidagdha Pitta

Amlodgara, Hrit-Kantha Daha, Utklesha, Aruchi

Amlapitta

AYURVEDIC ANALYSIS**Dosha**

Pradhana Dosha: Pitta (Pachaka Pitta) Anubandha Dosha: Kapha

Vata Involvement: Samana Vayu and Udana Vayu

Justification

- Amlodgara, Hrit-Kantha Daha indicate Pitta Prakopa.
- Utklesha, Aruchi, Saama Jihva indicate Kapha involvement.
- Urdhwaga manifestation in the form of sour belching suggests Udana Vayu Dushti.^[7]

Dushya

- Rasa Dhatu
- Anna Rasa
- Kleda

Justification

Improper digestion due to Agnimandya leads to formation of Vidagdha Anna and Ama, primarily affecting Rasa Dhatu and producing excess Kleda.^[8]

Agni

Jatharagni: Mandagni

Nature of Agni: Vishamagni progressing towards Tikshnagni due to aggravated Pitta.^[9]**Evidence**

- Avipaka
- Aruchi
- Utklesha
- Amlodgara

Ama

Present (Saama Avastha)

Evidence

- Saama Jihva
- Aruchi
- Avipaka
- Utklesha

Srotasa Involved^[10]

- Pradhana Srotasa: Annava Srotasa Moola:
 - 1) Amashaya
 - 2) Vama Parshva
- Anubandha Srotasa: Rasavaha Srotasa

Srotodushti Prakara^[11]

Annava Srotasa Sanga - Due to Agnimandya and Ama formation.

- Vimarga Gamana - Urdhwaga movement of Vidagdha Pitta causing Amlodgara.
- Rasavaha Srotasa Sanga - Due to impaired digestion and Ama formation.

Udbhava Sthana : Amashaya

As Amlapitta is primarily an Amashayagata Vyadhi with origin in the upper gastrointestinal tract.^[12]

Sanchara Sthana : Annava Srotasa

Adhithana: Amashaya and Urdhwa Annava Marga^[13]

Roga Marga: Abhyantara Roga Marga^[14]

Vyakta Sthana : Amashaya Manifested as:

- Amlodgara
- Hrit-Kantha Daha
- Utklesha
- Aruchi

Roga Swaroopa: Pittapradhana Tridoshaja Vyadhi^[15]

With predominance of:

- Pachaka Pitta Dushti
- Kledaka Kapha Dushti
- Samana Vayu Vaigunya

DISCUSSION

Amlapitta is a Pitta-pradhana disorder of Annava Srotasa resulting from Agnimandya and subsequent formation of Vidagdha Ahara. In the present case, the patient presented with classical features of Urdhwaga Amlapitta such as Amlodgara, Hrit-Kantha Daha, Aruchi, and occasional Utklesha. The history revealed significant Nidana Sevana in the form of irregular meal timings, excessive intake of spicy and oily foods, disturbed sleep, mental stress, and a sedentary lifestyle, all of which are recognized etiological factors for Amlapitta.

According to Ayurvedic principles, continuous exposure to these causative factors leads to vitiation of Doshas, predominantly Pachaka Pitta and Kledaka Kapha. Agnimandya develops initially, resulting in improper digestion of food and formation of Ama and Vidagdha Ahara. The vitiated Pitta acquires excessive Amla and Drava Guna, producing symptoms such as sour belching and burning sensation. The involvement of Kapha is evident from Aruchi, Utklesha, and Saama Jihva, indicating the presence of Ama.

From a contemporary perspective, the symptoms resemble hyperacidity or gastroesophageal reflux-related disorders, where excess gastric acid secretion and reflux

produce epigastric burning and acid regurgitation. The Ayurvedic concept of Vidagdha Pitta closely correlates with this pathological process. Thus, the case demonstrates the applicability of Nidana Panchaka, Dosh-Dushya analysis, and Samprapti understanding in establishing a comprehensive Ayurvedic diagnosis.

CONCLUSION

The present case was diagnosed as Urdhwaga Amlapitta based on classical Ayurvedic diagnostic parameters including Nidana Panchaka, Ashtavidha Pariksha, Dashavidha Pariksha, and Samprapti analysis. Improper dietary habits, irregular meal timings, disturbed sleep, stress, and sedentary lifestyle resulted in Agnimandya, Ama formation, and aggravation of Pachaka Pitta and Kledaka Kapha. The disease primarily involved Annava Srotasa with Amashaya as the Udbhava Sthana and Adhisthana.

This case highlights the importance of a systematic Ayurvedic diagnostic approach in understanding disease pathogenesis and identifying the underlying Dosh, Dushya, Agni, and Srotasa involvement. Accurate diagnosis through Roganidana facilitates appropriate treatment planning and emphasizes the significance of dietary and lifestyle modifications in the prevention and management of Amlapitta.

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